

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D7.2: Delivery of validated extraction protocols according to the treated biomass type.

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M1 to M22
Periodic report date and version:	30/04/2025
Deliverable D7.2 Responsible	Stefano Superchi (Unibas)
RM7 Responsible	Stefano Superchi

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
D7.1	Data on type, quality, availability, and geographical distribution of agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report and a database on distribution and availability of biomass suitable for valorization	UNIBAS	PU	M12
D7.2	Delivery of validated extraction protocols according to the treated biomass type	R	Report on validated methodologies for value-added extracts depending on biomass type	UNIBAS	PU	M22
D7.3	Extracts and pure compounds suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications and as biopesticides	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.4	Report on bio-chemical characterization of biomass extracts and pure compounds	R		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.5	Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.6	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report on validated methodologies suitable for scale-up and industrial production	UNIBAS	PU	M30

Table 2 - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M7.1	Survey on regional scale of the type, quality, availability, distribution of biomass from agro-forest waste	7	8	Report
M7.2	Selection of biomass materials suitable for valorization (at least three)	7	10	Report
M7.3	Validation of extraction protocols for selected matrices and materials	7	12	Report
M7.4	Availability of biomass extracts (at least five) suitable for bio-activity tests	7	16	Material
M7.5	Production of a report on bioactivity of different materials and compounds	7	20	Report
M7.6	Availability of biomaterials for bioactive material delivery	7	26	Material
M7.7	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	7	30	Report

INTRODUCTION

The final target of the Research Module 7 activity is the valorization of waste and by-products from the agro-forest industry of Basilicata through the production of valuable chemicals and intermediates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic, agriculture applications. To achieve this target, during the previous Deliverable 7.1 a data collection on agro-forest waste and by-products production of Basilicata has been carried out and the most promising waste for valorization have been selected. The selection has been carried out taking into account the waste availability, the environmental problems connected to the disposal, and the potential for valorization depending on the valuable metabolites content.

On the basis of such parameters waste coming from wine production (grape pomace, grape lees and grape stalks), those coming from pomegranate orchard (peel and seeds), those coming from olive oil production (olive pomace, mill waste water, olive stones) were selected as main targets. In addition, waste from pistachio production, from mushrooms cultivation, and from forest management were considered as further possible targets of studies for valorization.

Such biomasses were then studied for valorization by means of extraction of valuable bioactive metabolites. For each biomass, specific extraction methods have been tested evaluating the extraction performances and selectivity, the practicality and economy of the process, its environmental impact and its possible application on industrial scale.

Selection of extraction methodologies for biomass waste

Within the timeframe of this Milestone the studies on the evaluation of the extraction methodologies have been focused on two main biomass waste: those coming from winemaking and those related to pomegranate production. The biomass coming from olive oil production are currently under investigation but final results have not been achieved yet. This because the seasonal olive mill activity ended only in late December and waste (mill wastewater and pomace) were available only very recently. The results will be reported in the next Milestone reports.

a) Extraction methods of bioactive compounds from grape pomace.

Grape pomace is the main residue and waste from winemaking, together with wine stems and wine lees. Specifically, following alcoholic fermentation in the wine production process, approximately 10–30 % of the processed grapes' weight persists as solid organic waste, known as pomace, composed of stalks, skin, and seeds. Beyond the conventional practice of using grape pomace as animal feed and the production of distillates, various alternative uses for these valuable by-products have been explored.¹ One prominent alternative involves the extraction of bioactive molecules since it is known that approximately 70 % of the grapes' specialized

molecules, mainly polyphenols, are still in the pomace after the vinification process. In fact, during winemaking only a minor part of grape phytochemicals is extracted into the wine, leaving the pomace still rich in phenolic compounds (mainly flavonoids, phenolic acids, stilbenes and anthocyanins), dietary fibers, proteins, lipids and minerals.¹⁻⁴ Many of these compounds exert ascertained positive effects on human health⁴ and show a great potential of being applied as ingredients in the food, nutraceutical, pharmaceutical and cosmetic fields. Other components can be exploited as colorants, antioxidant or antimicrobial agents, or in packaging formulations.^{1,2,4,5,6}

The large availability of waste from winemaking and the richness of valuable bioactive metabolites of these wastes make them one of the most promising for recovery and valorization. Aim of the present study was to compare different extractive techniques' effects on three Aglianico grape pomaces from "Aglianico del Vulture DOCG" (Cantine del Notaio, Rionero in Vulture, PZ), Aglianico of Barile (PZ), and Aglianico from Torrecuso (BN). The efficiency of the chosen extractive methods in recovering specialized metabolites was evaluated using three different complementary antioxidant assays (TPC, FRAP, and DPPH tests). This allows for identifying the most promising extraction technique between the chosen conventional and unconventional ones. These latter were analyzed for the content of specialized metabolites, employing an innovative HRMS/ MS-based approach as molecular networking.

Optimization of the extraction process of Aglianico pomace fermented at room temperature for 7 days and then dried for 6 hours at 55°C was carried out. The aim of the study was to investigate the biological and phytochemical composition of the grape pomace starting from the comparison of different eco-friendly extractive methods, including conventional [such as maceration (MAC) and digestion (DIG)] and unconventional [such as microwave-assisted extraction (MW), ultrasound- assisted extraction (US), and accelerated solvent extraction (ASE)] extraction techniques.⁷ MAC is a low-cost extractive method performed at room temperature and is thus recommended for heat-labile molecule extraction, while DIG represents a modified version of maceration, allowing a possible increase in extraction yield through low heating application. Either MAC or DIG enables the dissolution of bioactive compounds *via* diffusion from plant material to solvent; however, in the case of DIG, the heat applied during the extraction process allows the solvent's viscosity to be lowered, thereby facilitating the extraction of secondary metabolites.⁸ MW is considered a novel extraction method applicable to extracting fluid-soluble products from a wide variety of plant materials by exploiting microwave energy to heat the solvent and plant material directly, determining a localized heating and rapid disruption of plant cells. The principle of microwave heating is hinged on the direct interactions of microwaves with molecules through two main mechanisms: ionic conduction and dipole rotation. Ionic conduction involves the movement of ions caused by an applied electromagnetic field, resulting in the solution's resistance to this ion flow generating friction, which in turn produces heat.⁹ ASE is another novel extraction technique based on applying high pressure and

high temperature to keep a solvent in a liquid state at temperatures above its normal boiling point. This elevated pressure enhances the extraction process, contributing to reduced extraction times and lesser solvent usage.¹⁰ Finally, another method used in the present investigation is UAE, which is based on the application of ultrasound waves which pass across the medium, generating alternating cycles of high and low pressure, resulting in the acoustic cavitation phenomenon. When cavitation bubbles collapse upon the plant material the inter-particle collision generate erosion, sonoporation, and cell rupture facilitating inorganic and organic molecules extraction from plant material.¹¹ All the cited techniques can be considered “green methods” applicable in recovering active compounds from by-products as they meet the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA).

The obtained extracts were tested for their antioxidant activity by the following complementary *in vitro* spectrophotometric assays: total phenol content (TPC) assay, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay, Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power assay (FRAP) assay, and β -carotene bleaching (BCB) assay.

Figure 1. Evaluation of antioxidant activity of grape pomace extracts (hydroalcoholic E/W, aqueous W) with different extraction methods (DIG, digestion; MAC, maceration; MW, microwaves; US, ultrasounds; ASE, accelerated solvent extraction) by means of different parameters (TPC, FRAP, DPPH, BCB). Different letters (a-e) indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0,05$).

In the case of the present investigation, by using MAC, DIG, MW, ASE, and US and environmentally friendly solvents like 50 % ethanol/ water, extractive yields ranging between 6.10 % \pm 0.85 and 13.36 % \pm 1.01 were obtained. Hence, the antioxidant activity of each extract obtained was evaluated. Free radicals represent a group of harmful molecules normally produced during the human body's cell metabolism. Due to the high levels of phenolic molecules, grape pomace represents a suitable by-product that is usable as a source of health-

promoting antioxidants. Results from the antioxidant activity evaluation in Figure 1 show that the highest antioxidant values were obtained for ASE. The efficacy of hydroalcoholic extraction compared to the aqueous one is confirmed by previous investigations on grape pomace in which it was seen that mixtures of methanol or ethanol with water are more effective than water used as a single solvent. This evidence indicates that ethanol may be a viable eco-friendly and safe alternative to methanol in extracting specialized metabolites from Aglianico pomace. Considering that the different antioxidant assays can provide different results based on the type of radical or oxidizing agent used, the RACI (Relative Antioxidant Capacity Index) was calculated to obtain an overall view of the activity of the extracts. The RACI is in fact a statistical index that relates the data obtained from different tests expressed with different units of measurement. The Relative Antioxidant Capacity Index (RACI) was calculated to compare the results obtained from DPPH, TPC, and FRAP assays with a view to identifying the most effective extraction method (Figure 2).

Figure 2. RACI (Relative capacity index) of extract made with different extraction methods (DIG, digestion; MAC, maceration; MW, microwaves; US, ultrasounds; ASE, accelerated solvent extraction) GP from Aglianico Grape of Cantine del Notaio (CNS), Torrecuso (T), and Barile (B).

The RACI allows confirmation of the effectiveness of the hydroalcoholic ASE extraction method and indicates the extract from Barile pomace as the most active, followed by Cantine del Notaio and Torrecuso grape pomace. The observed difference in the antioxidant activity of the different grape pomace varieties confirms previous observations since it was seen that the growing region of the wine, genotype, weather, and winemaking techniques may influence the phenolic amount and the antioxidant activity of wine by-products.¹²

Considering the RACI, it was decided to focus on ASE, as an unconventional extraction technique, and DIG, as a conventional extractive method. The extracts made by DIG are in fact the most active compared to those obtained with MAC, the other conventional extraction technique. Comparison through the RACI index highlighted that DIG has a lower relative antioxidant capacity than the extracts obtained with ASE and MW, but higher than those obtained with MAC. The RACI test made it possible to identify the hydroalcoholic extracts carried out using ASE and MW as the most active extracts. However, although these extraction techniques are environmentally sustainable, their large-scale industrial application is often complex. Therefore, following a review of the literature, the pomace was subjected to digestion (DIG) at 60°C for 2 hours. This conventional extraction method has proven to be economical and suitable for large-scale production, especially for small companies. Based on previously shown results, a 50% hydroalcoholic solution was chosen as the solvent. The extract thus obtained was evaluated for its antioxidant activity using the *in vitro* spectrophotometric assays previously used (Table 1).

Table 1. Evaluation of the anti-oxidant activity for extract obtained by digestion.

	TPC mgGAE/g	DPPH mgTE/g	FRAP mgTE/g	BCB %AA a 2.5 mg/mL
DIG E/W	242.70±18.68	559.72±41.64	515.85±43.52	85.64±5.82

Phytochemical analysis: In vitro spectrophotometric assays

An important quality factor for red wines is represented by polyphenols, which are highly related to wine sensory descriptors like structures, astringency, and bitterness. Amidst the by-products produced during winemaking, the pomace retains high total polyphenol content depending on the grape variety or winemaking techniques. A great deal of work has been devoted to developing analytical methods for determining grape polyphenolic composition with a view to planning interventions, from selecting the harvest date to controlling winemaking and wine aging processes. However, only a few investigations were performed on evaluating Aglianico Grape pomaces, and no extraction methods have been defined. Hence, the effect of two different extraction techniques, DIG (as a conventional extractive method) and ASE (as an unconventional extractive technique), coupled with hydroalcoholic solvent, were compared based on the recovery of tannins, flavonoids, and anthocyanins from different Aglianico grape pomace.

Tannins

The name Tannin is generally used to describe a polyphenolic nature complex biomolecule that has a sufficient number of hydroxyl and other groups, such as carboxyls, to form stable complexes with a wide variety of macromolecules. Tannins are secondary plant phenolic compounds commonly grouped into hydrolyzable and condensed tannins. In the context of the present investigation, the content of total tannins in Aglianico grapes pomaces varied between

1912.53 ± 128.95 and 2676.37 ± 223.86 mgTAE/g. Comparisons cannot be made with data present in literature due to the use of different measurement units; however, by analyzing individually the amount of condensed and hydrolyzable tannins, it was seen that the second one overcame the content of the first one. Hydroalcoholic DIG and ASE methods yield similar amounts of tannin, indicating that both extraction techniques are effective for obtaining these specialized metabolites.

Flavonoids and anthocyanins

Nearly 6000 flavonoid molecules have been reported in plants, classifying flavonoids as a significant family of secondary metabolites representing 13–30 % of the total phenolic content of red grapes. The most abundant flavonoids to be found in the grape are anthocyanins, which are present only in red pomace. In the present investigation, the amount of flavonoids varied from 405.88 ± 30.63 to 810.81 ± 51.61 mgQE/g, while that of anthocyanins ranged between 13.09 ± 0.75 and 17.08 ± 0.76 mgMA/g. The greatest quantity of anthocyanins was achieved in Torrecuso and Barile grape pomace varieties subjected to hydroalcoholic DIG, obtaining high values (from 5.3 ± 1.7 to 10.3 ± 1.4 mgMA/g). However, these differences may be related to berry ripening as a close correlation has been found between anthocyanin biosynthesis and the degree of berry ripeness. The highest levels of extracted flavonoids were achieved at high temperatures (60–90 °C).

In conclusion, using five eco-friendly extraction methods (MAC, DIG, MW, US, ASE), it was demonstrated that the choice of extraction technique significantly influences the bioactivity of the recovered compounds. Our results demonstrated that DIG emerged as the most effective technique, particularly for Barile grape pomace extracts. These findings suggest that DIG could be a cost-effective and industrially scalable method for producing high-value bioactive extracts. The major strength of this work lies in its integrative approach, combining eco-friendly extraction methods with advanced analytical techniques such as HRMS/MS and molecular networking. This latter allowed detailed metabolic profiling of Aglianico pomace extracts, identifying known and unknown compounds with promising antioxidant and chemopreventive properties. Additionally, the study highlights the potential of these extracts for their application in nutraceutical and pharmaceutical fields, contributing to the valorization of agro-industrial by-products.

b) Extraction methods of bioactive compounds from pomegranate waste.

Approximately 10 ha of pomegranate (predominantly of the Wonderful variety) are cultivated in the Basilicata region, yielding a total production of 400 tons. About 20% of the pomegranates are discarded during the harvest, while for pomegranate juice production, the amount of waste can reach up to 80% of the pomegranate's weight. The juice from pomegranates is one of nature's most powerful antioxidants as it has 3 times higher antioxidant activity than those of red wine and green tea.¹³ Pomegranate anthocyanins have scavenging activities, while its polyphenolic compounds elevate the antioxidant capacity of the human body.^{14,15} On average,

the pomegranate fruits contain 38%–50% juice, 39%–53% peel, and 8%–12% seed. Even if the overall waste production from pomegranate orchards in Basilicata is still quantitatively limited, the pomegranate production appears particularly promising for waste recovery and valorization activities for the large amount of waste produced during pomegranate juice and jams production.

Aim of the study was the comparison of different extraction methods of pomegranate waste taking into account their efficacy (in terms of yield of recovered total extract), its selectivity towards different classes of metabolites, its economy and scalability, its environmental impact and sustainability. In particular, traditional water/ethanol extraction was compared with innovative and *green* methods, such as deep eutectic solvents (DES),¹⁶ dimethylcarbonate (DMC), and methylTHF solvent. Different extracts were obtained from pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) waste coming from juice production. The samples were obtained from “Azienda Agricola Mercorella” di Scanzano Jonico (MT). The pomegranate fruit red-purple husk has an outer hard pericarp and an inner, spongy, mesocarp which comprises the fruit inner wall where seeds (arils) attach. At first, a crude alcoholic extract was recovered from waste containing residues of both husk and pressed seeds. The raw material was extracted with ethanol in a mechanical blender at room temperature. The suspension was separated by centrifugation and the solid separated from supernatant solution. The latter evaporated under vacuum provided the ethanolic extract. Subsequently, the ethanolic extract and the different parts of pomegranate (pericarp, mesocarp, seeds) were separately extracted with different DES to obtain fraction enriched in bioactive compounds. In fact, DES solvents are generally considered as non-toxic and environmentally friendly solvents. Moreover, DES solvents extracts could be used as they are in cosmetic preparations, without isolation of the bioactive components. Many different DES were then prepared by mixing Choline Chloride/Glycerol, oxalic acid, Urea, Levulinic acid, citric acid, lactic acid, ethylene glycol, glucose, fructose, or camphor/menthol (hydrophobic DES) in different molar ratios.

Table 2. DES Preparation

DES N	Hydrogen acceptor	Bond	Hydrogen donor	Bond	Molar Ratio
DES 1	Choline Chloride		Glycerol		1:2
DES 2	//		//		1:3
DES 3	//		//		1:4
DES 4	//		Oxalic acid		1:1
DES 5	//		Urea		1:2
DES 6	//		Levulinic acid		1:2
DES 7	//		Citric acid		1:1
DES 8	//		Lactic acid		1:1
DES 9	//		//		1:2
DES 10	//		Ethylene glycol		1:2
DES 11	//		Glucose		1:2
DES 12	//		Fructose		1:2
DES 13	//		Levulinic acid:urea		1:1:1
DES 14	Camphor		Menthol		1:1,7

Extraction with DES was carried out by mixing 500 mg of the exhausted pomegranate peels and DES/water (60:40 w/w) at a solid/liquid (S/L) ratio of 1:2 (w/w) and stirring at 70°C for 130 minutes. After the extraction, the samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 20 minutes at room temperature and the DES extracts were filtered through a syringe septum (pore size 0.45 µm). For analytical purposes, the extract was separated from the DES by back-extraction first with ethyl acetate and then with butanol. For biological assays and related applications of the extract in DES, no further treatment would be necessary after centrifugation. The samples prepared according to the described procedures were analyzed using ¹H NMR in D₂O. It was possible to identify various components in the extract, including glucose, fructose, alanine, threonine, glutamine, ellagic acid, punicalagin, GABA, and citrate. These findings were confirmed and enriched through comparison with LC-MS (Table 3 and Table 4).

Table 3. Complete Flavonoid Panel Investigated in Pomegranate Extracts by LC-MS/MS.

Flavonoid (mg/g)	EST9 Totale (EtOH)	EST10 Esocarpo (EtOH)	EST11 Arilli (EtOH)	EST12 Mesocarpo (EtOH)	EST37 (Mercorella)	EST38 DES	EST38-R Retroestratto DES	EST39 (MeTHF)	EST40 (DMC)	EST Evidente
Kaempferol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.11±0.01	nd
Phloretin	nd	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Myricetin	nd	nd*	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.19±0.01	0.19±0.01	0.19±0.01	nd
Polydatin	+	***	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Quercetin	nd	<LOQ***	nd	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Acacetin	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Baicalin	0.04±0.01	0.05±0.01	0.05±0.005	0.04±0.01	0.04±0.005	0.04±0.01	0.05±0.01	0.04±0.01	0.04±0.02	0.04±0.005
4-Hydroxychalcone	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
(+)-Catechin (Hydrate)	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Mangiferin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
(+)-Taxifolin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Diosmetin	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Morin	<LOQ	<LOQ	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
(-)-Epigallocatechin gallate hydrate	0.17±0.005	0.90±0.01	nd	0.13±0.005	0.19±0.005	0.15±0.005	0.20±0.005	0.40±0.01	0.33±0.005	0.27±0.005
Chrysin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
(+/-)-Naringenin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.01±0.005	0.02±0.005	0.02±0.005	0.01±0.005
Baicalin	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.01±0.005	0.01±0.005	0.01±0.005	0.02±0.005	0.016±0.002	0.01±0.005
Resveratrol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Luteolin	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Hesperidin	0.015±0.001	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Fisetin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
(-)-Epicatechin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Oxyresveratrol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Apigenin	0.04±0.005	0.04±0.005	nd	nd	0.04±0.005	0.03±0.005	0.04±0.005	0.04±0.005	0.06±0.001	0.04±0.005
trans-Pterostilbene	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Rutin Hydrate	<LOQ	0.31±0.01	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.02±0.005	0.01±0.005	0.12±0.005	0.06±0.005	0.004±0.001	0.04±0.005
Phloridzin	0.05±0.005	0.17±0.005	0.03±0.005	nd	0.05±0.005	0.04±0.003	0.11±0.003	0.16±0.01	0.38±0.02	0.11±0.001
Daidzein	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Hesperetin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.02±0.001	0.02±0.001	0.03±0.001	0.02±0.001
Puerarin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Isoliquiritigenin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Piceatannol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Biochanin A	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Formononetin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Diosmin	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Naringin dihydrochalcone	nd	<LOQ	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.12±0.003	<LOQ
Equol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Genistein	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd

*not detected; **detectable but not quantifiable; ***below Limit of Quantification.

Table 4. Complete Phenolic Acids Panel Investigated in Pomegranate Extracts by LC-MS/MS.

Phenolic Acids (mg/g)	EST9	EST10	EST11	EST12	EST37	EST38	EST38-R	EST39	EST40	EST Evidente
2,3-Dihydroxybenzoic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Chlorogenic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Syringic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
p-Coumaric acid	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
m-Hydrocoumaric acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Ferulic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Sinapic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Aspirin	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
trans-Cinnamic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	nd	<LOQ	nd	<LOQ	nd	nd	<LOQ	0.002±0.0006	0.01±0.001	nd
2,6-Dihydroxybenzoic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Dihydrocaffeic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Caffeic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	nd
Phloretic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Hydroferulic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Ellagic acid dihydrate	1.48±0.04	3.14±0.03	0.02±0.005	0.94±0.009	1.18±0.03	0.40±0.004	1.89±0.03	3.85±0.08	5.34±0.06	1.92±0.001
5-Methoxysalicylic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Catechol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Gentisic acid	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
4-Acetocatechol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
4-Methylcatechol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
2,6-Dimethoxybenzoic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Acetylphloroglucinol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Salicylic acid	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	nd	<LOQ	nd
trans-2-Hydroxycinnamic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Caffeic acid dimethyl ether	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
3-Methoxyhydrocinnamic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Gallic acid	0.2±0.005	0.1±0.001	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.08±0.004	0.05±0.005	0.4±0.007	0.86±0.003	1.24±0.04	0.14±0.007
3,5-Dihydroxybenzoic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.0015±0.001	<LOQ
Vanillic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Nordihydroguaiaretic Acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Terephthalic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
4-Acetylsorcinol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Rosmarinic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Caffeic acid phenethyl ester	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
2,3,4-Trihydroxybenzoic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
2,4-Dihydroxybenzoic Acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
3-Hydroxybenzoic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Coniferyl Alcohol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
m-Coumaric acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
2-Acetylsorcinol	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
3,4,5-Trimethoxycinnamic acid	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd

*not detected; **detectable but not quantifiable; ***below Limit of Quantification.

Extract from the pomegranate exocarp contains the highest relative concentration of polyphenols. The DES systems appear to be promising for selectively extracting specific components from exhausted pomegranate peels or from their individual parts.

Comparison Between Different Parts of Pomegranate: Est9 (Ethanol Extract of the exhausted pomegranate peels) vs. Est10 (Exocarp), Est11 (Arils), and Est12 (Mesocarp)

The baicalein content (a flavonoid with anti-inflammatory activity¹⁷) is identical across the various components, albeit present in small quantities (0.04 mg/g). The monohydrate epigallocatechin (with various biological properties, including antioxidant activity¹⁸) is predominantly found in the exocarp (0.9 mg/g), absent in the arils, and present at comparable concentrations in the total residue and the mesocarp (0.17 and 0.13 mg/g, respectively).

Hesperidin is found in small quantities (0.015 mg/g) exclusively in the total residue. Apigenin (noted for its antispasmodic activities¹⁹) is equally present in the total residue and the exocarp but is absent in the mesocarp and arils. Hydrated rutin (with significant antioxidant activities²⁰) appears to be present in appreciable amounts only in the exocarp. Phlorizin (anticancer, anti-obesity, antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-aging, antimicrobial, and melanogenic activities²¹) is primarily concentrated in the exocarp (0.17 mg/g) and, to a lesser extent, in the total residue and arils (0.05 and 0.03 mg/g, respectively), while absent in the mesocarp. Regarding ellagic acid (noted for neuroprotective, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, cardioprotective, antifibrotic, antiatherosclerotic, antiallergic, antinociceptive, antiestrogenic, skin-protective, wound-healing, osteogenic, antimicrobial, antiviral, and antiparasitic effects²²), it is particularly abundant in the exocarp (3.14 mg/g) and the total residue (1.48 mg/g), with smaller amounts in the mesocarp (0.94 mg/g) and trace amounts in the arils (0.02 mg/g). Ellagic acid is by far the most concentrated compound and biologically significant, suggesting that the biological potential of these extracts should be interpreted primarily in relation to ellagic acid content. Gallic acid (with excellent anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antitumor, antibacterial, antidiabetic, anti-obesity, antimicrobial, and myocardial ischemia protective activities²³) is present in the exocarp and the total residue (0.1 and 0.2 mg/g, respectively).

The extract of the total residue of the exhausted pomegranate peels and the exocarp extract are by far the most interesting extracts, as predicted from the ¹H NMR spectra. In particular, the exocarp extract (Est10) compared to the total residue extract (Est9) shows significantly higher concentrations of monohydrate epigallocatechin (0.9 vs. 0.17 mg/g) and ellagic acid (3.14 vs. 1.48 mg/g). These results appear to be corroborated by preliminary biological assays conducted on these four extracts.

Comparison Between Different Solvents on the extraction of the exhausted pomegranate peels

(Est37 - Ethanol vs. Est38 - DES 1 vs. Est38-R - Back-Extracted from DES 1 vs. Est39 - MeTHF vs. Est40 - Dimethyl Carbonate)

Kaempferol²⁴, associated with reducing the risk of cardiovascular diseases, certain cancers, neurodegenerative diseases, infections, diabetes, osteoporosis, anxiety, and allergies, was found at relatively interesting concentrations exclusively in the DMC extract (0.11 mg/g). Myricetin²⁵, known for its anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antibacterial, antiviral, anti-obesity, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, and hepatoprotective activities, was present in identical amounts in the back-extract, the MeTHF extract, and the DMC extract (0.19 mg/g) but was absent in the ethanol and DES1 extracts. The content of Baicalein, Epigallocatechin Gallate, Naringenin, Baicalin, and Apigenin did not show significant differences between the various extracts. The only notable difference concerned the content of Epigallocatechin Gallate, which was slightly higher in the MeTHF extract (0.4 mg/g) compared to the other extracts. The content of Hydrated Rutin was

higher in the back-extract (0.12 mg/g) and lower in the DMC extract (0.004 mg/g). The content of Phlorizin in the DMC extract was eight times higher than that in the ethanol extract (0.38 vs. 0.05 mg/g) and twice as high as in the MeTHF extract (0.38 vs. 0.16 mg/g), while Naringin Dihydrochalcone was only found in the DMC extract.

The most important data concerns Hydrated Ellagic Acid, which was significantly higher in the DMC extract (5.34 mg/g), although it was also considerable in the MeTHF extract (3.85 mg/g) compared to the ethanol and back-extract samples (1.18 and 1.89 mg/g, respectively). The same trend was observed for Gallic Acid, whose concentration in the DMC extract was 15 times higher than in ethanol and 40% higher than in MeTHF. The DMC extract is undoubtedly the most promising, followed closely by the MeTHF extract. The ethanol extract appears to be the least promising. However, it is not entirely possible to assess the efficiency of DES, as the Est38 data refers to a solution of the extract in DES, while the Est37 data (ethanol extract) refers to a dry ethanol extract. A proper comparison between extracts in solution from both solvents is needed for an accurate evaluation. Although the back-extract (Est38-R) shows a better profile than the ethanol extract, this is due to the higher selectivity of MeTHF for the compounds in question and cannot be directly attributed to better efficiency or selectivity of DES compared to ethanol. Nonetheless, the back-extract from DES has an interesting profile, highlighting the effectiveness of the back-extraction method. Another important compound, Punicalagin²⁶, not listed in the database, would be quantified in the extracts for further analysis.

The DMC extract demonstrates the best profile, a particularly interesting finding given the apparent lack of publications on pomegranate waste extraction using this solvent (a green solvent²⁷). However, selective extraction with DMC and MeTHF has been reported in grape pomace studies.

Further analyses could be conducted on pomegranate extracts in various DES (listed in table 1) and compared to ethanol extracts (in solution) to determine the best solvent. However, performing biological assays in DES may be challenging due to compatibility issues. Back-extraction with MeTHF or DMC could be considered. Biological assays will be conducted on ethanol, MeTHF, and DMC extracts in order to compare them. Subsequently, metabolomic profiling of various DES extracts will be performed, with biological tests conducted on the most promising one.

CONCLUSION

Biomass samples were treated with innovative low impact and 'green' extraction methodologies like ultrasound assisted extraction, microwave assisted extraction, accelerated solvent extraction, hydrothermal treatment, and deep-eutectic solvents. Extract mixtures and isolated pure compounds coming from biomass extraction were then tested for their biological properties. Antioxidant activity was evaluated through spectrophotometric tests: β -carotene

bleaching (BCB) assay, FRAP assay and radical DPPH inhibition assay, and the metabolite content analyzed by LC-MS.

As far as the grape pomace extraction is concerned, different eco-friendly extraction methods (MAC, DIG, MW, US, ASE) were employed, demonstrating that the choice of extraction technique significantly influences the bioactivity of the recovered compounds. Our results demonstrated that DIG emerged as the most effective technique, particularly for grape pomace extracts. These findings suggest that DIG could be a cost-effective and industrially scalable method for producing high-value bioactive extracts.

Pomegranate waste were instead treated with either traditional water/ethanol extraction or innovative and *green* methods, such as deep eutectic solvents (DES),¹⁶ dimethylcarbonate (DMC), and methylTHF solvent. The DMC extract was undoubtedly the most promising, followed closely by the MeTHF extract, while the ethanol extract appears to be the least promising. The efficiency of DES need to be further investigated, particularly in respect to the methodology of back-extraction. In fact, the back-extract from DES has an interesting profile, highlighting the effectiveness of the back-extraction method.

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